

**FABRICATION OF N-I-P MESOSCOPIC PEROVSKITE SOLAR
CELLS VIA ONE-STEP AND TWO-STEP DEPOSITION METHODS:
A COMPARATIVE STUDY**

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THESIS CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “Fabrication Of n-i-p Mesoscopic Perovskite Solar Cells Via One-Step And Two-Step Deposition Methods: A Comparative Study,” submitted by Anwar M K to the Department of Nanoscience and Technology, Central University of Jharkhand, Ranchi in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of Master of Technology in Nanoscience and Technology, is an authentic record of research work carried out by the student under my supervision. The contents of this thesis, in full or in parts, have not been submitted separately to any Institute or University for the award of a degree or diploma.

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(ANWAR M K)

Declaration

I certify that

- a. The work contained in this thesis is original and has been done by myself under the general supervision of my supervisors.
- b. The work has not been submitted to any other Institute for degree or diploma.
- c. Whenever I have used materials (data, theory and text) from other sources, I have given due credit to them by citing them in the text of the thesis and giving their details in the reference section.

Anwar
14/07/20

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AM 1.5	Air mass of 1.5
ETL	Electron transporting layer
Exciton	Excited electron-hole pair
FF	Fill factor
HTL	Hole transporting layer
ISC	Short circuit current
IV-curve	Current voltage curve
J _{sc}	Short circuit current density
PSC	Perovskite solar cell
PCE	Power conversion efficiency
R _s	Series resistance
R _{SH}	Shunt resistance
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
XRD	X-ray Diffraction
QE	Quantum Efficiency
HTM	Hole Transporting Material
ETM	Electron Transporting Material
LUMO	Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbital
HOMO	Highest Occupied Molecular Orbital
UV-Visible	Ultraviolet Visible
MA/CH ₃ NH ₃	Methyl Ammonium
MAI/CH ₃ NH ₃ I	Methyl Ammonium Iodide
PbI ₂	Lead iodide
DMF	Dimethylformamide
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
TiO ₂	Titanium dioxide

ABSTRACT

Perovskite solar cells (PSC) are low cost and high efficiency photovoltaic technology fabricated through simple solution processed deposition methods. Small area n-i-p mesoscopic perovskite solar cells are fabricated through both one-step and two-step deposition methods with methyl ammonium lead iodide (MAPbI₃) as the light harvesting material. A detailed comparison between both the methods helps to understand the differences in photovoltaic performance of the cell. The mesoscopic structure helps in reducing the recombination rate of charge carriers and also provide more surface area for the charge carriers which enhance the device performance. The electron and hole transporting layers as well as the perovskite films are deposited by spin coating. The metal contact has been made by thermal evaporation. From the UV-Vis transmittance spectra, the transparency of electron transporting layer has been found out. The absorbance spectra of the active perovskite layer provide information about the light spectrum harvested by the solar cell which is crucial for the device performance. Scanning electron microscopy images of different layers has been taken which provide information about the crystallinity and morphology of the layers. Solar simulator with a source-meter has been used to evaluate the values of different photovoltaic parameters such as short circuit current density, open circuit voltage, fill factor, power conversion efficiency, series and shunt resistances, which define the cell performance. A statistical analysis of the solar cell parameters gives the clear picture of the cell performance in both one-step and two-step fabrication methods. The values of all solar cell parameters by two-step method are superior to that by one-step deposition. The solar cells fabricated by two-step deposition show higher power conversion efficiency than one-step processed cells.

Keywords: Perovskite solar cell, mesoscopic structure, one-step and two-step deposition, spin coating, power conversion efficiency.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Energy is essential to life and all living organisms. The world needs an increased energy supply to support economy, development and to build better quality of life. Currently, about 75% of the world's energy requirements are satisfied by fossil fuels which have adverse effect on human health and environment. The demand for energy increases on daily basis which may lead to energy crisis in the world. The main reason for this crisis is the limited availability of the non-renewable energy resources. Non-renewable energy resources such as fossil fuels produce greenhouse gases and polluting agents which cause global warming and climate change. Therefore, the development of eco-friendly renewable energy resources such as solar, wind, geothermal and tidal has become a necessity. Renewable energies sources are clean and environment friendly. They are inexhaustible in nature and they neither produce greenhouse gases nor emit hazardous pollutants. They differ from fossil fuels in their diversity, abundance and low cost.

Due to its abundance, low cost and non-localized nature, solar energy-based technologies such as photovoltaics (PV) and solar thermal have got more attention in recent years. Solar energy is the key to a clean energy future. Every day, the sun gives us more energy than we need to power everything on earth. The advantages of solar energy over fossil fuels are: they don't release any harmful emissions to the air, they do not require any fuels for their functioning, it can use unutilized land and it also improves grid security. Environmental impact of solar power is significantly smaller as compared to other technologies. It has very low cost because we get solar energy freely. Solar panels can be installed on roof tops which increases efficiency due to the less electricity loss as a result of short transmission distance. Since the durability of the solar panels is high, service interruption can be reduced significantly. Apart from the

application of solar energy as a technology for electricity production, it is also possible to use solar energy for heating purposes like solar thermal system which converts sunlight into heat [1].

1.1 SOLAR CELL

A solar cell is basically a p-n junction which generates voltage when solar radiation falls on it. Solar cells work on the principle of photovoltaic effect. Generally, silicon wafers are used to make the p-n junction which are available in large quantities and very effective due to their electronic properties. A p-n junction is formed by taking a silicon wafer and doping it with trivalent and pentavalent impurities. Fig 1.1 shows the basic structure of a solar cell consisting of both p and n-type semiconductors, front and back electrodes and antireflection coating to reduce the losses due to reflection of light.

Fig 1.1: Structure of a solar cell

1.2 SOLAR SPECTRUM

The spectrum of the sun is similar to that of a black body and has a temperature of 5778 K. This peak lies in the visible region of the spectrum and has a tail in the infrared range. For measuring solar cell efficiency in laboratories, the standard AM1.5G (air mass 1.5 global) spectrum is used as reference. AM1.5G corresponds to a power density of 1000 W/m². Fig 1.2 shows the spectrum of AM0 and AM1.5 taken from National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) database [2].

Fig 1.2: AM0 and AM1.5 solar spectrum, National Renewable Energy Laboratory

When a material has a large bandgap, it won't be able to absorb significant number of photons. When the bandgap of the material is very small, it will be able to absorb large number of photons but energy loss will occur due to the thermalization losses associated with the absorption of high energy photons. Therefore, there exists a trade-off between efficiency and bandgap of the material. Hence, we can find out theoretical maximum efficiency of the cell and optimum bandgap of the material. Shockley and Queisser determined this maximum theoretical

efficiency for a single junction solar cell which is known as Shockley-Queisser limit which is approximately 33% and corresponds to a bandgap of 1.34 eV. Therefore, semiconductors with bandgap close to 1.5 eV are ideal material for solar cell fabrication such as Silicon, Cadmium Telluride, Gallium Arsenide etc. The important criteria for the selection of a material for solar cell fabrication include bandgap, high optical absorption, good electrical conductivity, availability of the raw material and more importantly production cost. Fig 1.3 shows the relationship between maximum theoretical efficiency and optimum bandgap of the material [3].

Fig 1.3: Relation between maximum theoretical efficiency and optimum bandgap

1.3 WORKING OF A SOLAR CELL

The generation of current by a solar cell when illuminated with sun light is the result of three basic processes that take place in the cell. These processes are the generation of charge carriers, separation of charge carriers and collection of charge carriers. When the energy of the incident

sunlight is greater than the band gap of the material there will be generation of significant number of electron-hole pairs in the depletion region which is also known as the space charge region. The subsequent separation of generated charge carriers takes place due to the electric field which is already present in the depletion region. The electrons are swept to the n side and holes to the p side. The electrons reaching the n side will be collected by the front contact and the holes reaching the p side will be collected by the back contact. Therefore, the p side becomes positively charged and n side becomes negatively charged which results in the generation of a photovoltage and this is called the photovoltaic effect. When an external load is connected to the device a photocurrent flows through the load from p side to n side which can be driven out as the output power. Fig 1.4 shows the working of a solar cell [4].

Fig 1.4: Working of a solar cell

1.4 SOLAR CELL CHARACTERISTICS

A solar cell is characterized by the following four basic parameters: short circuit current, open circuit voltage, fill factor and efficiency. Short circuit current is the maximum current that flows in a solar cell when its terminals at p-side and n-side are shorted with each other. Maximum short circuit current is obtained in a solar cell when there is no recombination of

charge carriers taking place in the device. Short circuit current is a function of the band gap of the material and decreases when the bandgap increases. For silicon having a band gap of 1.1 eV, the maximum short circuit current obtained is 46 mA/cm². Open circuit voltage is the maximum voltage generated across the terminals of a solar cell when they are kept open. Fill factor is the ratio of maximum power that can be extracted from a solar cell to the ideal power. Fill factor represents the squareness of the solar cell I-V curve. Efficiency is defined as the ratio of the power output to power input. The power output is the maximum power point of a solar cell and input power is the power of solar radiation [5].

The maximum power can be found using the equation 1.1

$$P_{max} = V_{OC}I_{SC}FF \quad (1.1)$$

The efficiency can be found using the equation 1.2

$$\eta = \frac{V_{OC}I_{SC}FF}{P_{in}} \quad (1.2)$$

Current-voltage measurements are carried out to obtain the solar cell parameters. A series of voltages are applied and the output current of the cell is measured at each voltage step when the cell is under light illumination. All the results are plotted on a graph and I-V curve is obtained. For solar cells, current density is obtained instead of normal current because the output current is directly dependent on the solar cell area. The I-V graph is plotted in the fourth quadrant. Solar cells work in the fourth quadrant since the power is driven out from the device. Fig 1.5 shows the I-V curve of a solar cell [6]. For ease of visualization, I-V graphs are generally plotted in the first quadrant.

Fig 1.5: I-V curve of a solar cell

Equivalent circuit is a model used to understand the electronic behaviour of a solar cell. It is a combination of a current source, resistors and diode. The equivalent circuit is obtained by connecting a diode in parallel with the current source as shown below. To represent the various losses in the cell a shunt resistance and a series resistance is connected to it. Series resistance is used to represent the energy losses within the different layers of the cell, at their interfaces and external contacts. Shunt resistance describes the alternate paths of current through the solar cell and is an indicator of the quality of material used in fabricating the solar cell. To achieve high power conversion efficiency, series resistance and shunt resistance should be very low and very high respectively. Fig 1.6 shows the equivalent circuit of a solar cell [7].

Fig 1.6: Equivalent circuit of a solar cell

1.5 WHY WE NEED TO GO BEYOND CURRENT SOLAR CELL TECHNOLOGIES?

Solar cell technologies are an attractive option for clean and renewable energy generation in the form of electricity. But photovoltaic (PV) solar electricity is not economical in comparison to the grid power which we use today. The first major limitation of silicon photovoltaic (PV) cells is that they are made from a material that is rarely found in nature in pure form rather it exists in the oxide form. Oxygen content is removed by melting silicon dioxide at 1500–2000 °C in an electrode arc furnace. This heating process requires huge amount of energy which limits their production and results in high cost and also greenhouse gases are released during this process. The main reason for the high cost of present PV modules is the high cost of the ultrapure silicon base material mostly used in today's solar cell technologies. Si solar cells which contribute to 90% of the world's market are made from single crystalline and monocrystalline silicon. Due to their high purity and stability devices having an efficiency of about 25% can be fabricated. But the high cost of ultrapure silicon combined with a large material consumption results in a high cost of the finished PV panels. The weight and the rigid nature of the silicon solar cells is also a concern. Silicon solar cells work best when they are flat and housed in large, heavy panels. But those panels make large-scale installations very expensive, and that is why silicon solar panels are mainly seen on roof tops and in big solar farms. The other concern related to conventional solar cells is their power conversion efficiency (PCE) which has been stuck at 25% for the last 10 years. Due to these limitations of conventional silicon solar cells, in the last few decades much of the research effort has shifted towards solar cell fabrication on very thin substrates, which consumes less material, resulting in a different class of solar cell technology known as thin film solar cells. These technologies include amorphous silicon, thin film polycrystalline silicon, polycrystalline Copper Indium

Gallium selenide (CIGS), polycrystalline Cadmium Telluride, organic solar cells, quantum dot solar cells (QDSC) and Perovskite Solar Cells (PSC's) [8].

1.6 PEROVSKITE SOLAR CELLS (PSCs)

Perovskites are a class of compounds which have the same type of crystal structure as CaTiO_3 . The general chemical formula for perovskite compounds is ABX_3 , where A and B are cations (size of A is greater than B) and X is a halogen atom. In the cubic structure, A cations sit at cube corner positions, B atom sit at body centre position and oxygen/halogen atoms sit at six face centred positions. Both orthorhombic and tetragonal phases are also displayed by perovskite compounds. For the structural stability of the compound, the Goldschmidt tolerance factor should lie between 0.75 – 1. Fig 1.7 shows the crystal structure of methyl ammonium lead iodide in which MA (methyammonium) atoms sits at the cube corners, iodide ions at the face centred positions and lead atom at the centre [9].

Fig 1.7: Crystal structure of methyl ammonium lead iodide

Organic inorganic hybrid perovskites have emerged as a class of light harvesting materials for photovoltaic applications and have shown rapid increase in power conversion efficiencies. This new technology emerged a decade ago and the first perovskite solar cell was fabricated in 2009. Since then, over a time period of ten years, perovskite solar cell efficiency has increased steadily and reached up to 23%. This rapid progress has been achieved by simple solution processed fabrication methods that have made the PSC's a high performance but low-cost photovoltaic technology. Success of perovskite solar cells is attributed to the intrinsic material properties shown by the perovskite material such as easy processing, high absorption coefficient, long carrier diffusion length, flexible band gap tuning, defect tolerance and suitability for fabrication on flexible substrates [10]. The organic inorganic hybrid perovskite that we have used in our present work is methylammonium lead tri iodide (MAPbI_3) which has a band gap of 1.55 eV.

1.7 DEVICE ARCHITECTURE

The most popular and common device structures for PSC's is divided into three types, namely n-i-p mesoscopic, n-i-p planar and p-i-n planar or inverted structure. The mesoscopic structure contains an electron transport layer (ETL) scaffold with nanoscale pores over a transparent conducting oxide which acts as an electrode. The perovskite absorber layer covers the scaffold with a compact capping layer and penetrates in to the scaffold forming an intermixing layer. The mesoporous layer facilitates charge separation and helps in reducing the hysteresis loss. Then, a hole transporting material (HTM) and a metal contact which can be gold, silver or copper act as the second electrode. In mesoscopic structure, mesoporous materials are used because of their high porosity and large specific surface area. It allows the perovskite absorber to adhere to the mesoporous metal oxide for increasing the light-receiving area of the

perovskite material and improving the efficiency of the device. TiO_2 is mostly used as the mesoporous material, which allows the perovskite nanocrystals to penetrate into the pores of mesoporous TiO_2 and forms an interconnected absorbing layer. This kind of structure reduces the recombination probability of electrons and holes, but also provides the required diffusion length for the effective collection of electrons and holes.

The n-i-p planar architecture uses only a compact ETL layer and removes the perovskite-ETL intermixing layer. The remaining components are similar to that of mesoscopic structure. The p-i-n structure is generally called the inverted structure because the carrier extraction is inverted from the initial n-i-p planar structure. A key advantage of the mesoscopic over planar architecture is that it is suitable for collection of almost all photogenerated charge carriers even for materials where the charge carrier diffusion length is much shorter than the absorption length [11]. Fig 1.8 shows the device architectures of mesoscopic, n-i-p planar and inverted perovskite solar cells.

Fig 1.8: n-i-p mesoscopic, n-i-p planar and inverted perovskite solar cell

The basic function of ETL is to form an electron selective contact with the perovskite light absorbing layer. ETL helps to improve the extraction efficiency of photo-generated electrons and effectively prevent the hole from migrating to the counter electrode. ETL enhances the charge carrier separation and reduces the recombination rates. The selection of an electron transport material is based on the following properties. Firstly, n-type semiconductors having higher carrier mobility are selected. Secondly, the material should be transparent to visible light due to a relatively wide band gap. Thirdly, the preparation conditions should be mild and the material can be obtained at low temperatures. Finally, the band structure should appropriately match that of the perovskite materials. At present, TiO₂, which has a wide band gap (3.2 eV), has been extensively used as an effective electron transport material. The main role of the hole transport layer is to collect and transport holes from the perovskite light-absorbing layer. In hole transport materials, for effective hole transport the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) must match the valence band of perovskite materials. Hole transporting materials are divided into two types: organic and inorganic hole transport materials. Spiro-OMeTAD is the most commonly used organic hole transport material, which shows good penetration in perovskite and is a good match with the valence band energy of perovskite [12].

1.8 WORKING OF A PEROVSKITE SOLAR CELL

When a cell is illuminated with solar radiation, the photons from the sun reach the perovskite layer through the glass and the transparent electrode. In the active perovskite layer, the photon is absorbed and excites an electron-hole pair if the energy of the photon is higher than the bandgap of the perovskite material. The bound electron hole pair is known as an exciton. The exciton is separated to free charge carriers by the internal potential created from the work function difference between the transparent electrode and the metallic electrode. The electrons

are transported to the ETL while the holes are transported to the HTL. From there the electrons are transported to the transparent electrode and the holes to the metallic electrode. Finally, the electron moves through the wire connecting the two electrodes and a current is produced by the moving electrons. To reduce the recombination of electrons and holes, the ETL's Lower Unoccupied Molecular Orbital (LUMO) is made a bit lower than the active layers LUMO which creates a different path for the electrons to go. Similarly, HTL's HOMO is made a bit higher than the active layers HOMO which creates a different route for holes. This is same for every layer in the cell, each layer has either higher HOMO or lower LUMO [13]. Fig 1.9 shows the energy band diagram of different layers of a perovskite solar cell [14].

Fig 1.9: Energy band diagram of different layers of a perovskite solar cell

1.9 PRESENT WORK

In the present work, n-i-p mesoscopic perovskite solar cells are fabricated through both one step and two step deposition methods at ambient conditions, and detailed comparison of their results have been carried out. The complete fabrication process, starting from preparation of the conducting glass substrates, and ending with solar cell characterization by I-V and quantum efficiency (QE) measurements is a 36-40 hours process. In the n-i-p mesoscopic structure, we used fluorine doped tin oxide (FTO) as an electrode, titanium dioxide as electron transport layer, methylammonium lead iodide as the active perovskite layer, Spiro-OMeTAD as the hole transport layer and silver/copper metal contact as the second electrode.

First, substrate has been cut into the desired size. This was followed by etching and cleaning process. Both ETM and mesoporous layers were deposited by spin coating. The active perovskite layer is deposited by both one step and two step solution method. HTM layer is then spin coated and silver metal contact is made by thermal evaporation. The necessary heat treatments were done in between the spin coating steps. In this way, a large number of n-i-p mesoscopic perovskite solar cells were fabricated. We have compared the results of the one-step and two-step processes. A schematic of both one step coating and two step coating are shown in Fig 1.10 [15].

Fig 1.10: One step and two step coating

The transmittance of both ETM layer and mesoporous layers were obtained using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Scanning electron microscopy images of both ETM and mesoporous layers are taken to see the microstructure. To confirm the crystal structures x-ray diffraction patterns were collected for both ETM and mesoporous layer using an x-ray diffractometer. The absorbance spectra of the perovskite layers made by both one and two step methods were found with the help of UV-Vis spectrophotometer in the visible and near infrared wavelength region. The I-V characteristics are obtained using a solar simulator and Keithley source meter. From I-V measurements, open circuit voltage, short circuit current density, maximum peak power, fill factor, efficiency, series resistance and shunt resistance are obtained. After getting the above results for both the methods, a comparison has been carried out.

CHAPTER 2

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 SPIN COATER

Spin coating is a solution-based process used for depositing uniform thin films on flat substrates and the instrument used for this process is known as a spin coater or spinner. Spin coating starts with the dilution of the material to be deposited in a solvent and the solution is subsequently dispensed on the substrate surface. The substrate is then rotated with high speed in order to spread the coating material by centrifugal force. Rotation is continued with the fluid until the solution uniformly spread across the substrate material and stops when the desired thickness of the film is achieved. The thickness of the film depends on the angular frequency, viscosity and the concentration of the solution and the solvent. Fig 2.1 shows the spin coater instrument.

Fig 2.1: Spin coater, APEX, EZ Spin A1

The relationship between thickness and the angular speed can be expressed as

$$t \propto 1 \div \sqrt{\omega} \tag{2.1}$$

Where, 't' is thickness of the film and 'w' is angular speed of the spin coater. Equation (2.1) is called the spin coating thickness equation.

2.2 UV-VISIBLE SPECTROPHOTOMETER

Ultraviolet visible spectroscopy uses light from the visible and ultraviolet regions of the electromagnetic spectrum to excite electrons from the ground state to the excited state. If the energy gap between highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) is lower, electrons will get excited more easily and absorb light of longer wavelength. The instrument used in UV-Visible spectroscopy is called UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer. It uses radiant energy in the far and near ultraviolet, visible and near infrared regions of the electromagnetic spectrum for characterization of materials. The instrument operates by passing a beam of light through a sample and measuring wavelength of light reaching a detector.

Transmittance (T) can be found as

$$T = I/I_0 \quad (2.2)$$

Where, I represent the intensity of light after passing through the sample and I_0 is the intensity of light before passing through the sample. The energy of the light transmitted from the sample is measured using a photo detector, which gives the absorbance of the sample.

According to Beer-Lambert's law, Absorbance (A) of a material is directly proportional to the concentration of the sample and its thickness.

$$A = -kcl = \log(I_0/I) = \log(1/T) \quad (2.3)$$

Where, A is the absorbance, c is the concentration of the sample, l is the path length travelled by light or thickness of the material and k is a constant known as molecular extinction coefficient.

Fig 2.2 shows the components and experimental setup of UV-Vis spectrophotometer [16]. Fig 2.3 shows the UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Fig 2.2: Components of UV-Visible spectrophotometer

Fig 2.3: UV-Visible spectrophotometer, **Shimadzu UV 2600**

2.3 THERMAL EVAPORATOR

Thermal evaporation is a type of physical vapour deposition used to make thin films over different substrates. The instrument used for this purpose is known as thermal evaporator. It is based on the principle of joules heating. Evaporation involves the vaporization of a material by way of a resistive heating. The vaporised material is subsequently deposited on a target as a thin film. This process relies on the fact that when heated, particularly under a very low pressure in the order of 10^{-5} pascal there is a finite vapour pressure over all materials. Thermal energy is supplied by passing a large current through a crucible or basket which is usually a thermally tolerant material (tungsten) holding the source material. The resistivity of the crucible generates sufficient heat such that the source material is vaporised as atoms. The vaporised source material travels through low pressure space to fall upon a target sample, where it condenses to form a film. The solid material either sublimates or evaporates. This process is achieved in a vacuum chamber. Fig 2.4 shows the components of a thermal evaporator [17].

Fig 2.4: Components of a thermal evaporator

In most cases, the source material is heated from solid to liquid before vapour. Therefore, the source material is supported from beneath. Vaporised source material rises up towards a downward facing target sample. A quartz crystal sensor enables control of the source material vaporisation rate. This rate control is coupled with a movable shield to allow specific film thickness deposition on the sample. Evacuation of the chamber gases is required before source material deposition on the sample.

First a rough pump reduces pressure inside the chamber to around 10^{-2} Pa. Next, a turbo pump reduces pressure inside the chamber to less than 10^{-2} Pa (10^{-5} Pa). Resistive heating vaporises the source material. Quartz sensor is used to set the vaporization rate. Once desired rate is set, the shield is moved to reveal the sample. Resistive heating vaporises the source material onto the sample. Vaporised source material impinges on the substrate surface where it settles and condenses. Once a film of desired thickness is obtained, the shield is returned to cover the sample and resistive heating is slowly ceased. This results in a thin film of source material

covering the sample surface. The method is directional due to a large mean free path of the vaporised source material, alloys have different vapour pressures and are challenging, and the deposited film adhesion can be poor. These are the advantages of a thermal evaporator. The advantages include limited damage to the sample and the deposited films are very pure. Fig 2.5 shows the experimental setup of a thermal evaporator.

Fig 2.5: Thermal evaporator, VEC solutions, Bengaluru, India

2.4 SOLAR SIMULATOR

Solar simulator provides the voltage and current relationship of a solar cell by plotting the I-V curve which in turn gives an information about the various electrical parameters as well as the efficiency of the cell. Solar simulator provides uniform solar radiation and gives standard

constant light intensity (1000 W/m^2 or 1 sun) without any fluctuations. The information obtained from the I-V curve is used to evaluate the solar cell performance in terms of its efficiency, short circuit current, open circuit voltage, fill factor, series resistance, shunt resistance and peak power.

The solar simulator uses an artificial light source whose illumination spectrum matches with that of sun. Arc lamps usually Xenon or Mercury arc lamps are preferred to use as the light source because their radiation spectrum nearly matches with that of sun at AM1.5. Before placing the fabricated solar cell for measurement, a standard reference cell is used to verify whether the instrument parameters are in proper working condition by plotting the I-V curve both in normal and dark current modes. The light when incident on the solar cells generates current and voltage and that are measured with the help of a data acquisition system (DAS). The active area of the cell is fixed. An internal sweep circuit applies either current or voltage and the measurement circuit measures the other quantity which is either voltage or current respectively. In this way the current-voltage curve of the solar cell is obtained. The information from the I-V curve is then used to calculate the short circuit current (J_{SC}), open circuit voltage (V_{OC}), fill factor (FF), peak power, applied current, applied voltage, series resistance, short circuit resistance, efficiency etc in tabular form. The solar simulators are manufactured to provide standard test conditions (STC) for solar cells. The simulator works at irradiation levels of 1000 W/m^2 and at AM1.5 spectrum. To match the standard solar spectrum some filters are also used in solar simulators. A temperature control system is set up which properly maintain the solar cell temperature as that of the room temperature (about $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The back side of the solar cell is placed in a metal chuck which is cooled down by the flowing water. The metal acts as a back contact of the cell [8]. Fig 2.6 shows the image of a solar simulator.

Fig 2.6: Solar simulator, AAA Class, 50 cm x 50 cm Uniformity Area, SS-F5-3A, Enlitech,
Taiwan

2.5 QUANTUM EFFICIENCY (QE) MEASUREMENT

This instrument is used to obtain the performance of a solar cell for different wavelengths of light. It can provide the quality of solar cell fabrications such as surface texture, surface passivation and material quality information like diffusion length, minority carrier lifetime etc. It also provides information about the response of the solar cell junction when illuminated by light. The internal quantum efficiency (IQE) calculations are used to find out the minority carrier lifetime, diffusion length, and surface recombination velocity at the front and back surface of the solar cells.

The quantum efficiency is defined as the ratio of the number of carriers collected by a solar cell to the number of photons of a given energy incident on the solar cell. It is the probability of an incident photon resulting in generation and collection of an electron in the solar cell. That is how electrons are generated and collected which is contributing to the current flow for each incident photon. Quantum efficiency is represented either as a function of wavelength or

energy. For each photon maximum one electron can be generated, if it is not recombined then it will contribute to the current flow in the cell resulting in the maximum quantum efficiency value 1 or we say, 100%. The quantum efficiency (QE) is measured in the short circuit mode of the cell and the short circuit current is measured for incident photon of one wavelength at a time.

External quantum efficiency can be found as

$$EQE = \frac{\Delta J_{sc}}{q\Delta\phi\lambda} \quad (2.4)$$

Internal quantum efficiency can be found as

$$IQE = \frac{EQE}{1-R-T} \quad (2.5)$$

Where, ' J_{sc} ' is the incremental short circuit current in the cell, ' ϕ ' is incremental photon flux, ' R ' is reflectance of the solar cell and ' T ' is transmittance of the solar cell.

Only photons which are absorbed by a solar cell contributes to the solar cell current. Neither reflected nor transmitted radiation contribute to output power, therefore most commonly internal quantum efficiency measurement is used to study the solar cell performance. In QE test, a light of different wavelength is generated with the help of a monochromator and diffraction gratings. The light of different wavelengths is incident one by one on a solar cell which is operating in a short circuit mode. Due to the light incident on the solar cell surface, a current is generated which varies for different wavelengths of incident light. The measured current is then plotted against the incident wavelength. By following the same method quantum efficiency of a cell is measured. Reflectance can be measured with the help of IQE test. The transmittance of the cell is usually neglected because it is assumed that, the cell is thick enough to absorb complete spectrum.

QE analysis is used to examine a cell at different regions because photons of different wavelengths are absorbed at different wavelengths. The absorption length in a solar cell indicates the generation range of carriers up to which photon of given wavelength will generate electron-hole pairs. High energy blue photons are absorbed very close to the surface within few 100 nm, the green photons are absorbed within few micrometres from the surface and the red photons are absorbed within few hundred micrometres. This implies that for high energy or short wavelength blue photons, only the area from the front surface to the junction is active. For medium wavelength photons, the junction area and the nearby area are active while for the long wavelength photons nearly the whole solar cell area is active. These conditions are most applicable to wafer based solar cells, but it is slightly different for thin film solar cells where cell thickness is very less, in the range of few micrometres. Light trapping set up is used in thin film solar cells which make the light travel back and forth in the cell [8]. Fig 2.7 shows the experimental setup of a QE measurement system.

Fig 2.7: Quantum efficiency measurement system, Voltage and Light Biasing Facility, QE-R, Enlitech, Taiwan

2. 6 DEVICE FABRICATION

2.6.1 Apparatus and Chemicals Required

Table 2.1 lists the apparatus and instruments required for the fabrication and characterization of perovskite solar cell.

FTO	Spatula	Micro filter	Multi meter
Table scale	Tweezer	Micro tips	Four-probe set up
Marker	Freezer	Micro pipette	Silver paste
Vials	Aluminium foil	Desiccator	Silver pellets
Beaker	Paraffin	Vacuum oven	Optical microscope
Scissor	Tissue paper	Vacuum pump	Spin coater
Scotch tape	Butter paper	Hot plate	Solar simulator
Kapton tape	Air blower	Electronic balance	Thermal evaporator
WC glass cutter	Vortex mixer	Connecting wires	X-ray diffractometer
Cotton	Magnetic stirrer	Stop watch	UV-Vis spectrometer
Substrate holder	Ultrasonic bath	Humidity sensor	SEM
Syringe	UV Ozone cleaner	Thermometer	QE measurement

Table 2.1: Instruments and apparatus required

2.6.2 Solutions and Chemicals Required

Table 2.2 shows the solutions and chemicals used for the fabrication of the perovskite solar cell.

Solution	State	Company name
Zinc dust	Powder	Sigma Aldrich
Hydrochloric acid	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich
Acetone	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich
Ethanol	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich
Isopropyl alcohol	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich
Titanium isopropoxide	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich
TiO ₂ paste	Gel	Sigma Aldrich
TiCl ₄	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich
Lead iodide	Powder	Sigma Aldrich
Methyl ammonium iodide	Powder	Sigma Aldrich
Toluene	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich
Chlorobenzene	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich

2-Propanol	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich
N, N-Dimethyl formamide	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich
Dimethyl sulfoxide	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich
Acetonitrile	Liquid	Sigma Aldrich
Spiro-OMeTAD	Powder	Sigma Aldrich
4-Tert-Butyl-Pyridine	Powder	Sigma Aldrich
LiTFSI	Powder	Sigma Aldrich

Table 2.2: Solutions and chemicals used

Glass of thickness 2 mm coated with Fluorine doped Tin Oxide (FTO) is purchased and cut into small pieces of dimension 1 by 1 inch. 70% of the substrate is covered with a scotch tape which is resistant to acid and 30% is left for chemical etching to make conducting electrode. The chemical etching is done by treating the uncovered portion of the sample with zinc powder and diluted hydrochloric acid (HCl). 38 ml of deionized water is added in 13 ml concentrated hydrochloric acid. Etching is done until the resistivity is reduced to zero. After etching, substrate is cleaned in distilled water and the scotch tape is removed and taken for further cleaning processes. Fig 2.8 shows the schematic of chemical etching procedure. Fig 2.9 shows the images of substrate holder, sample cleaning procedure using ultrasonic bath and UV ozone cleaner.

Fig 2.8: HCl, Zinc dust and chemical etching respectively

The samples are kept inside a beaker using a substrate holder made of Teflon and then cleaned in an ultrasonic bath. The samples are cleaned in the ultrasonic bath using deionized water, acetone, and isopropanol. Each cleaning step is carried out for 20 minutes at room temperature. Ultrasonic cleaning uses cavitation bubbles induced by high frequency pressure waves to agitate a liquid. The agitation produces high forces on contaminants adhering to the substrate and thereby making the sample contaminant free. Further the sample is cleaned in an UV ozone cleaner for 15 minutes at room temperature at 100% emissivity. The organic contaminants that present in the sample is removed by UV ozone surface treatment in which organic compounds are converted into volatile substances by decomposition by ultraviolet rays and by strong oxidation during the formation and decomposition of O_3 , and are removed from the contaminated surface.

Fig 2.9: Substrate holder, Ultrasonication of the samples and UV ozone cleaning respectively

2.6.3 Electron Transport Layer (ETL) deposition

Preparation of c-TiO₂: Ethanol is taken in a vial using a micropipette and a solution is made by adding titanium tetrakis-isopropoxide (TTIP) in a ratio of 39:10 by volume in ml. The solution is shaken gently, filtered using a microfilter and paraffin is used to prevent the evaporation. Then the spin coater is opened and cleaned. Main switch of spinner turned on and vacuum switch started. After the warm up and calibration of the spinner is done, program is loaded. Fig 2.10 shows the ETL deposition process using a spin coater.

Fig 2.10: Schematic of ETL deposition

For electron transporting layer deposition (c-TiO₂), FTO coated sample is taken from the UV ozone cleaner and 1 by 4 portion of the sample is covered using a Kapton tape. Remaining portion of the sample is used for ETL deposition using spin coater. In a micropipette, ETL solution is taken and spin coated over the substrate. Rotation per minute (RPM) has kept 3000 and acceleration time has taken as 30 seconds. After spin coating, samples are post annealed in a hot plate starting from a temperature of 100 °C to 500 °C with a ramping temperature of 50 °C. The sample is then held at 500 °C for 30 minutes. Finally, the samples are taken from the hot plate after cooling for sufficient time. Fig 2.11 shows ETL solution. Stirring using vortex mixer and annealing of ETL on a hot plate.

Fig 2.11: c-TiO₂ solution, vortex stirring and heat treatment of c-TiO₂ film

2.6.4 Mesoporous Layer Deposition

Titanium dioxide paste and ethanol are mixed in a vial in 2:7 (w/w) ratio. With the help of vortex mixer, the solution is made homogeneous and transparent. Mesoporous titanium dioxide is then spin coated over the electron transporting layer with 5000 RPM for 30 seconds. The prepared mesoporous film is then taken for post annealing in a hot plate. The annealing started from 50 °C for 5 minutes. Temperature raised to 125 °C, 350 °C and kept at these temperature for 5 minutes. Finally, samples were kept at 500 °C for 30 minutes. Sufficient time was given for cooling and the samples are taken out of hot plate.

To reduce the recombination rates of charge carriers and to improve the crystal quality of the film, mesoporous coated sample is then treated with titanium tetrachloride (TiCl₄). TiCl₄ solution was prepared by mixing TiCl₄ with deionized water ice in a specific ratio in a vessel at room temperature. The mesoporous TiO₂ covered samples were placed into the TiCl₄ solution in the vessel on hot plate, keeping the temperature of the solution at 70 °C. After heating the samples are taken out, rinsed with DI water, and dried using an air blower at room

temperature. After drying, all the samples are annealed again on a hot plate 550 °C for 30 minutes.

2.6.5 Perovskite Layer Deposition

The active perovskite layer can be deposited either by one step method or two step method.

One Step Coating: In one step coating, 461 mg lead iodide (PbI_2) and 158 mg methyl ammonium iodide (MAI) are mixed. 200 μl DMSO and 800 μl DMF (1:4 ratio) are added to the mixed solution. The solution is placed on a hot plate at room temperature and heated to 180 °C for 10 min. The PbI_2 powder dissolves within 15 min resulting in a clear looking solution. Then they left for cooling to room temperature. The solution can be stored for a long time, however reheating to 180 °C is required each time. The perovskite film is deposited by spin coating. The precursor solution is taken in a two-step protocol: a slow step (10 s at 1000 rpm and 200 rpm/s) to ensure full surface coverage after dropping the solution in the middle of the substrate and a subsequent fast step (20 s at 6000 rpm and 2000 rpm/s). During the second step, the antisolvent is dropped with a pipet in the middle of the rotating substrate. Before 5 seconds to the end of the spinning, 200 μL of chlorobenzene (the antisolvent) is rapidly dropped in the middle of the substrate. Dropping too rapidly can induce a hole in the middle of the substrate; dropping too slowly can induce cracks in the final film. Additionally, aiming the antisolvent towards the middle avoids a hole in the middle. Following the spin-coating step, the substrates are placed immediately on a hot plate preheated at 100 °C for 40–60 min. Before annealing, the perovskite film should look semi-transparent, brown-like-coloured. It should turn opaque black after a few minutes on the hot plate. After annealing, the film surface should look smooth and shiny. Any inhomogeneity, pinholes, cracks, or a hazy-looking surface can affect the device performance [19]. Fig 2.12 shows lead iodide solution, MAI solution and heating of the perovskite precursor solution. Fig 2.13 shows MAI films obtained after one step coating.

Fig 2.12: Heating of perovskite precursor solution, filtered PbI_2 and MAI solutions respectively

Fig 2.13: MAI films after one step coating

Two Step Coating: In two step method both layers of lead iodide (PbI_2) and methyl ammonium iodide (MAI) are spin coated separately. To make the PbI_2 precursor solution PbI_2 is dissolved in N-N dimethyl formamide (DMF) at a concentration of 462 mg/ml under stirring at 70 °C for 18 hours. The solution is filtered through a 0.45 μm PTFE filter and then kept at 70 °C while stirring during the whole procedure. The mesoporous TiO_2 films are infiltrated with PbI_2 solution by spin coating at 4000 RPM for 30 seconds to form a transparent yellow layer. The samples are dried on the hot plate at 80 °C for 10 minutes. After cooling the samples to room

temperature, a solution of MAI in isopropanol was spin coated on top of the PbI_2 layer at 2000 rpm for 30 seconds, which was dried at 110°C for 10 minutes thereby forming the perovskite layer. During the spin coating process, the colour of the sample changed from yellow to dark brown confirms the formation of perovskite. After that the absorbance of the perovskite coated sample is measured with the help of double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Fig 2.14 and Fig 2.15 shows the formation of perovskite layer after coating lead iodide and methyl ammonium iodide by two step coating method.

Fig 2.14: Heating of PbI_2 and MAI films

Fig 2.15: PbI_2 and MAI films prepared by two step deposition method

2.6.6 Hole Transport Layer (HTL) Deposition

Preparation of Stock Solution: 4-tert-Butylpyridine (tBuP) liquid solution was prepared by solution growth method. In this process 4-tert-Butylpyridine (tBuP) has taken in a vial and

make a solution with Acetonitrile in the ratio of 1:1. Then solution is mixed by gently shaking the vial. Lithium bis (trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide (LiTFSI) solution was prepared by mixing LiTFSI 170 mg/ml in Acetonitrile. The mixing of solution is done by gently shaking vials.

Preparation of Spiro-OMeTAD Solution: Spiro-OMeTAD Solution was prepared by conventional solution processing method. In this process we take Spiro-OMeTAD Solution 70 mg/ml in Chlorobenzene. Then both stock solution and Spiro OmeTAD solution are mixed by gently shaking vials. Spiro-OmeTAD layer was spin coated at 2000 rpm for 30 seconds. Fig 2.16 shows the sample after HTL deposition and fig 2.17 shows the different types of solutions prepared for the deposition of different layers of a perovskite solar cell.

Fig 2.16: Samples after hole transport layer coating

Fig 2.17: Different solutions prepared for perovskite solar cell fabrication a) c-TiO₂, b) m-TiO₂, c) PbI₂, d) MAI and e) Spiro-OMeTAD respectively

2.6.7 Metal Electrode Evaporation

Silver and copper metal are used as the counter electrode of the solar cell. The contact is made by thermally evaporating the copper atom. Smaller tungsten boats and less quantity of copper is used to avoid unnecessary heating of sample. The vacuum pressure of the system has kept at 10^{-6} Pa. The heating process is started by applying current through the chamber. The temperature of the sample has kept between 40-50 °C. Slow deposition rates are preferred to get uniform thickness. Evaporation is carried out until the desired thickness of the metal is obtained (120 nm-130 nm). Fig 2.18 shows the metal electrode evaporation process.

Fig 2.18: Thermal evaporation of the metal

Fig 2.19: Perovskite solar cells fabricated by one step and two step coating method respectively

The fabrication of n-i-p mesoscopic perovskite solar cell by simple solution deposition method can be shown in the following simple flow chart.

Fig 2.20: Fabrication of PSC, the whole fabrication steps in a single image

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 UV-VIS TRANSMITTANCE SPECTRA

The transmittance of compact TiO_2 (c- TiO_2) and mesoporous TiO_2 (m- TiO_2) coated over both glass and FTO are found out using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Transmittance data has taken with respect to air. Transmittance data is plotted in which the Y axis measures the transmittance in percentage and X axis represents the experimental wavelength in nano meter scale. The maximum value of transmittance is 100 in percentage. The wavelength range for the experiment has kept between visible and near infrared wavelength region (400 nm to 800 nm) that is, the experiment starts from near infrared wavelength region and covers the entire spectrum and ends there itself.

Fig 3.1 shows the transmittance graph of c- TiO_2 in which the red curve represents c- TiO_2 coating over FTO and the green curve is for c- TiO_2 coating over glass. In both cases the transmittance is low in the beginning of the experiment. Transmittance gradually increases as we go from near infrared wavelength region to the visible region. Transmittance of c- TiO_2 over FTO is greater than the transmittance of c- TiO_2 over glass in the visible region whereas the situation reverses once the wavelength reach near the infrared region. The difference in the shape of red curve is due to the surface roughness of FTO. The glass surface is smooth hence the curve shape looks normal.

Fig 3.1: Transmittance versus wavelength graph of c-TiO₂

In a similar way, transmittance of mesoporous TiO₂ (m-TiO₂) over both FTO and glass are found. Fig 3.2 shows the transmittance graph of both the cases. Here, black curve represents the transmittance of m-TiO₂ over FTO and red curve represents the transmittance of m-TiO₂ over glass. Here also transmittance of m-TiO₂ over FTO is greater than that over glass in the visible region and the situation reverses in the near infrared wavelength region. From both the figures it is clear that transmittance of c-TiO₂ is greater than that of m-TiO₂. Fig 3.3 shows the transmittance of FTO without coating (black curve), FTO with c-TiO₂ coating (red curve) and FTO with m-TiO₂ coating (blue curve).

Fig 3.2: Transmittance versus wavelength graph of m-TiO₂

Fig 3.3: Transmittance of FTO with and without coating

3.2 SEM IMAGES

The scanning microscopy images of both c-TiO₂ and m-TiO₂ coated over FTO are taken to see the microstructure. Fig 3.4 and 3.5 respectively shows the SEM images of c-TiO₂ and m-TiO₂ at 10000x magnification.

Fig 3.4: SEM image of c-TiO₂

Fig 3.5: SEM image of m-TiO₂

Fig. 3.6 shows the three-dimensional complex structure of fragmented rice pellet like structure morphology of the perovskite layer. The morphology is uniform throughout and is made up of small grains. However, the dense microstructure has observed throughout the film. The aggregate is formed by covalent bonding between particles and then several aggregates interact with each other through van der Waal force to give secondary structure known as agglomerate.

Fig 3.6: SEM top view image of CH₃NH₃PbI₃

3.3 X-RAY DIFFRACTION PATTERN

3.3.1 XRD Pattern of Anatase TiO₂

The structural characteristics of the TiO₂ film have been examined by X-ray diffraction spectra as shown in the figure 3.7. The diffraction peaks are taken to confirm the crystal structure. X-

ray diffraction patterns are taken after holding the TiO₂ film at 450 °C for 1 hour. At 450 °C TiO₂ exists in anatase phase. The image shows the diffraction peaks of anatase TiO₂. The diffraction peaks of the calcined sample match those of tetragonal structure of anatase TiO₂ with the space group of I41. XRD pattern shows strong diffraction peaks at (110), (220) planes characteristics for TiO₂ in the tetragonal phase with lattice parameter $a = 3.7845 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 9.5143 \text{ \AA}$. The 2θ at peak 25.4° confirms the TiO₂ anatase structure. Strong diffraction peak at 48° indicating TiO₂ in the anatase phase.

Fig 3.7: XRD pattern of anatase TiO₂

3.3.2 XRD Pattern CH₃NH₃PbI₃

The structural characteristics of the CH₃NH₃PbI₃ film have been examined by X-ray diffraction spectra as shown in the figure 3.8. The diffraction peaks of the calcined sample match those of tetragonal structure of CH₃NH₃PbI₃ with the 4-mc/m space group. XRD pattern shows that the films composed of single pristine perovskite phase with strong diffraction peaks at (110), (220)

and (114), characteristic for $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ in the tetragonal phase with lattice parameter $a=8.87\text{\AA}$ and $c=12.67\text{\AA}$. The solvent molecules expand the interlayer distance along with c-axis by intercalating among PbI_2 layers. Therefore, the peaks for adducts appeared at lower angles compared with that of pure PbI_2 , as shown in figure 3.10. No peaks of PbI_2 could be detected. PbI_2 phase in pure perovskite can be identified by the characteristic PbI_2 peak located at $2\theta \sim 9.45$. The absence of additional peak in the spectra denotes the phase purity of the annealed samples and the sharp peak visualizes the crystallinity of the samples.

Fig 3.8: XRD pattern of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$

3.4: COMPARISON BETWEEN ONE-STEP AND TWO-STEP DEPOSITION METHODS

3.4.1 UV-Vis Absorbance Spectra

The absorbance of the active perovskite layer prepared by both one step and two step coating method is measured with the help of a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The absorbance spectra of the perovskite films are obtained by plotting the absorbance in X axis and wavelength (in nm) in the Y axis. The wavelength range is kept from the visible region to the near infrared wavelength region (400 nm to 800 nm).

Fig 3.9 shows the absorbance graph of perovskite films of five different samples prepared by one step coating method. In the figure SA, SB, SC, SD, and SE represents sample A, sample B, sample C, sample D and sample E respectively. The absorbance of the film increases slowly once the wavelength varies from the near infrared region to the visible region. From the absorbance graph it is clear that the active perovskite layers absorb photons from the solar radiation and generates significant number of electron-hole pairs. If the absorbance of the film is high then the generation of charge carriers will be high. The absorbance of the perovskite film directly influences the performance of the device. For a highly efficient device high absorbance of the perovskite film is favoured. The absorbance of the perovskite films prepared by two step coating is greater than that of the films prepared by one step coating due to the uniform crystallization and high morphology of the films.

Fig 3.9: Absorbance spectra of perovskite films prepared by one step coating method

Fig 3.10 shows the absorbance graph of perovskite layers of five different samples prepared through two step coating method.

Fig 3.10: Absorbance spectra of perovskite films prepared by two step coating method

3.4.2 Photovoltaic Performance of the Cell

Table 3.1 and Table 3.2 respectively lists the solar cell parameter values such as short circuit current, open circuit voltage, maximum power, Fill factor, efficiency, series resistance and shunt resistance of seven different n-i-p mesoscopic solar cells (A to G) fabricated through two step and one step coating methods. The photovoltaic characteristics of the n-i-p mesoscopic solar cells are tested with standard AM 1.5G spectrum under 1 sun (100 mW/cm^2) condition. The active cell area of the solar cell fabricated through two step coating is 0.30 cm^2 and the active cell area for one step coating is 0.15 cm^2 .

Device Name	Area (cm^2)	Current density, J_{SC} (mA/cm^2)	Open circuit voltage, V_{OC} (V)	Maximum power, P_{max} (mW)	Fill factor, FF (%)	Efficiency (%)	Series resistance, R_{S} (ohm)	Shunt resistance, R_{SH} (ohm)
A	0.30	15.04	0.84	2.24	28.67	3.62	88.93	89.94
B	0.30	16.21	0.75	2.18	27.53	3.35	66.94	183.1
C	0.30	15.66	0.78	2.67	27.25	3.33	57.13	50.41
D	0.30	14.32	0.74	1.83	31.19	3.31	105.8	57.73
E	0.30	13.82	0.73	0.85	32.42	3.27	114.5	109.1
F	0.30	13.06	0.72	1.49	34.00	3.20	71.47	63.75
G	0.30	12.56	0.69	1.09	34.91	3.03	86.33	430.8

Table 3.1: Solar cell parameter data for two step method

Device Name	Area (cm²)	Current density, J_{SC} (mA/cm²)	Open circuit voltage, V_{OC} (V)	Maximum power, P_{max} (mW)	Fill factor, FF (%)	Efficiency (%)	Series resistance, R_s (ohm)	Shunt resistance, R_{SH} (ohm)
A	0.15	6.39	0.57	0.53	27.59	1.00	135.98	245.98
B	0.15	9.04	0.39	0.51	27.84	0.98	65.76	103.69
C	0.15	7.02	0.51	0.47	26.23	0.94	137.33	160.12
D	0.15	5.0	0.43	0.31	28.15	0.61	145.61	210.11
E	0.15	5.37	0.39	0.29	27.41	0.57	122.20	173.87
F	0.15	5.43	0.39	0.29	27.02	0.57	118.12	157.31
G	0.15	3.37	0.52	0.25	32.15	0.56	642.18	1071.38

Table 3.2: Solar cell parameter data for one step method

3.4.3 Stability Data

Table 3.3 shows the solar cell parameter data of the same five devices of one step method measured after two months. The samples are stored in the desiccator at ambient conditions. The devices still show some appreciable solar cell parameter values even after two months from fabrication.

Device Name	Short circuit current density, J_{SC} (mA)	Open circuit voltage, V_{OC} (V)	Maximum power, P_{max} (mW)	Fill factor, FF (%)	Efficiency (%)	Series resistance, R_s (ohm)	Shunt resistance, R_{SH} (ohm)
1	1.87	0.65	0.094	48.62	0.59	632.96	7150.4
2	1.55	0.65	0.083	51.71	0.52	671.06	9311.2
3	1.07	0.61	0.073	69.20	0.46	578.35	4752.9
4	0.71	0.59	0.052	75.78	0.33	1255.6	6408.6
5	1.00	0.61	0.049	49.87	0.30	1887.4	4400.2

Table 3.3: Solar cell parameter (one step method) data after two months

3.4.4: J-V Curve of the Solar Cell

Fig 3.11 shows the current density-open circuit voltage curve of the n-i-p mesoscopic perovskite solar cell fabricated through one step coating method. The device shows a power conversion efficiency of 1.00% with open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) value of 0.57 Volts, current density (J_{SC}) value of 6.39 mA/cm² and a fill factor of 27.59%. Fig 3.12 shows the J-V curve of the cell for the two -step method having open circuit voltage, current density and fill factor values of 0.84 volts, 15.04 mA/cm² and 28.67% respectively. The device shows a power conversion efficiency of 3.62%.

Fig 3.11: J-V curve of the solar cell fabricated by one step coating

Fig 3.12: J-V curve of the solar cell fabricated by two step method

3.4.5 Mean, Median and Standard deviation of solar cell parameters

A statistical analysis of photovoltaic parameters of seven cells from each coating method has been carried out. Table 3.4 lists the mean, median and standard deviation values of the solar cell parameters such as current density, open circuit voltage, maximum power, fill factor, efficiency, series resistance and shunt resistance for both one step and two step coating methods.

Solar cell parameters	Two step coating			One step coating		
	Mean	Median	Standard deviation	Mean	Median	Standard deviation
Current density (mA/cm ²)	14.38	14.32	1.34	5.95	5.43	1.78
Open circuit voltage (V)	0.75	0.74	0.05	0.46	0.43	0.07
Maximum power (mW)	1.76	1.83	0.66	0.38	0.31	0.12
Fill factor (%)	30.85	31.19	3.10	28.05	27.59	1.95
Efficiency (%)	3.30	3.31	0.18	0.75	0.61	0.21
Series resistance (ohm)	84.44	86.33	20.83	196.74	135.98	198.81
Shunt resistance (ohm)	140.69	89.94	135.70	303.20	173.87	341.64

Table 3.4: A statistical analysis of solar cell parameters of one step and two step deposition methods.

Both one step and two step solution processed deposition methods are easy to practise and frequently used for the fabrication of perovskite solar cells in the laboratory at ambient and other conditions. The absorbance of the perovskite film in the visible and near infrared wavelength region prepared by two step coating method is greater than that prepared by one step coating. The power conversion efficiency of the solar cell prepared by two step coating is far greater than that of one step. The highest efficiency of the device by two step coating has been 3.62% with a small standard deviation of ± 0.18 whereas the highest efficiency achieved through one step coating has a value of 1.00% with a small standard deviation of ± 0.21 . From the comparison of both the coating methods and their mean, median and standard deviation values of the various solar cell parameters, it can be found that devices fabricated by two step coating method shows better photovoltaic performance than one step coating. All the parameters of two step deposited perovskite are superior to those of one step deposited one. Average short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), fill factor (FF), and power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 5.95 mA/cm², 0.46 V, 0.28, and 0.75% are observed from the one-step deposited perovskite solar cells, while higher values of 14.38 mA/cm², 0.75 V, 0.309, and 3.30% are obtained from the two-step deposited ones. Standard deviation for PCE is ± 0.21 and ± 0.18 for the one step and two step deposited devices respectively.

One step deposition is simple and easy to perform as compared to two step deposition method. The superiority of two step coating over one step coating can be explained by the following properties. The main reason for this variation is due to higher voltage and fill factor of the extremely thin perovskite layer. The good performance and high efficiency of the device is due to the optimized film thickness and the uniform perovskite layer. The uncontrolled precipitation of perovskite layer in a single step deposition produced large morphological variation. The TiO₂ layer is not completely covered by the perovskite using one step coating method compared to full coverage with perovskite by two step coating method. Insufficient coverage in one step

coating is due to the wettability which is associated with high ionic strength of coating solution and the competition between positive ions of CH_3NH_3 and lead atoms. Imperfect pore filling of perovskite by one step coating leads to contact between FTO and HTM, whereas pores are completely filled perovskite by two step coating. One step coating produces shapeless perovskite crystal whereas two step coating produce cubes like crystals. One step coating lead to perovskite island but two step results in void free perovskite layer. Morphology-property relation can be used to explain the difference in photovoltaic performance. Higher J_{SC} for the two-step deposition is due to better pore filling of perovskite compared to its island structure for the one step deposition. The absence of perovskite at FTO interface loses absorption of short wavelength light, which is responsible for lower J_{SC} for one step deposition. Hence, it can be concluded that two step deposition method gives better and effective photovoltaic performance.

CHAPTER 4

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Conclusion

Small area n-i-p mesoscopic perovskite solar cells were successfully fabricated through one step and two step coating methods. The XRD results indicate the presence of perovskite structured compound belonging to the tetragonal crystal system. UV-visible studies confirmed the range of absorption spectra of the perovskite material in the visible wavelength region. The transmittance properties of ETL and the transparent conducting oxide were also studied. The SEM image showed the pin hole free structure of the perovskite film.

Perovskite cells fabricated via one-step method showed an efficiency drop of about 40% from their initial value after two months of fabrication. The samples were stored under dark conditions in a desiccator. This experiment showed that, with proper encapsulation, perovskite solar cells can operate for a very long time, up to several months and years.

Large number of n-i-p mesoscopic solar cells were fabricated. The highest power conversion efficiency of 3.62% was achieved with copper metal coating through two step deposition method, whereas an efficiency of 1.00% was achieved with copper coating in one step deposition method. A comparison of the various solar cell parameters such as short circuit current density, open circuit voltage, fill factor, efficiency, maximum power, series resistance, shunt resistance etc for both one step and two step methods was carried out and also their mean, median and standard deviation values were tabulated for easy analysis of the result. From the comparison data it is clear that the two-step sequential deposition is better than one step deposition since it gives a higher power conversion efficiency. Also, the two-step deposition method provides more reproducible results.

Scope for the future work

1. Fabrication of perovskite solar cell with gold metal contact.
2. Try to understand the factors that influence the stability of the cell and develop highly stable device architectures.
3. Fabrication of large area perovskite solar cells at ambient conditions.
4. Design a model for fabricating stable perovskite solar cells at different environmental conditions.
5. To understand the hysteresis behaviour of the perovskite solar cell.
6. To improve the performance of perovskite solar cells by studying interface behaviours and experimenting with new materials.

CHAPTER 5

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